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Germ layer-specific expression of fibroblast growth factor.

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Endoderm specification required FGF17 and FGF8, and ectoderm specification was qualitatively similar in FGF requirement. Mesoderm specification from human embryonic stem cells required, in addition to FGF17 and FGF8, the growth factors FGF3, FGF10, FGF9 and FGF19. Mesoderm lineage commitment requires additional growth factor input for fate specification.